

Crimes against a Person in the Ukrainian Criminal Law of the 15th – 16th Centuries

У статті розглядаються поняття, основні риси та характеристики ключових видів злочинів проти особи – вбивства та посягань на здоров'я. Доведено, що у нормах Литовського Статуту було закріплено поділ злочинів проти особи на вбивства та посягання на здоров'я. Поняття вбивства мало як загальні, так і специфічні терміни, які відображали спосіб позбавлення життя або суб'єктивну сторону. З'ясовано, що у правовій пам'ятці була зафіксована класифікація вбивств залежно від різних критеріїв, зокрема, поділ у залежності від форми вини (умисні та вчинені з необережності). Виявлено, що у III редакції Литовського Статуту розмежовано прямий та побічний умисел, злочинну самовпевненість та недбалість, що впливало на міру покарання. Встановлено, що нормативно було закріплено й інший вид вбивства – залежно від стану злочинця й жертви. За однотипні вбивства шляхтичі несли менш сувору кримінальну відповідальність, ніж простолюдини. Доведено, що вбивства поділялись залежно від статі, і за заподіяння смерті жінці винний сплачував подвійну винагороду. У нормах Литовського Статуту знайшов відображення поділ умисних вбивств залежно від наявності (кваліфіковані) або відсутності (прості) обтяжуючих обставин. У нормах правової пам'ятки було закріплено поділ злочинів проти здоров'я на кілька груп у залежності від тяжкості спричиненої фізичної шкоди потерпілому (спричинення каліцтва, поранення, побої), що впливало й на міру покарання. Виявлено, що кожний вид мав спеціальну термінологію. Розвиток поглядів законодавця на поняття злочинів проти здоров'я був відображений у Литовському Статуті 1588 року, у нормах якого зафіксовано урізноманітнення видів каліцтва, а також введення як покарання принцип «таліону». З'ясовано, що злочини проти здоров'я поділялись за тими самими критеріями, що й вбивства: форма вини (умисел чи необережність), соціальний статус і стать злочинця та потерпілого, обтяжуючі обставини. Встановлено, що розвиток поняття злочинів проти особи протягом XVI ст., тенденції ускладнення поняття, основних рис та характеристик вбивства й посягання на здоров'я зумовлювались такими причинами: розвитком духовної сфери (підвищення рівня правосвідомості законодавця, вплив християнської релігії), особливостями суспільного ладу Великого князівства Литовського та Речі Посполитої (сталість станового поділу населення), специфікою внутрішнього політичного становища держави (формування відносин васалітету).

Ключові слова: Україна, українське кримінальне право, генеза, джерела права, види злочинів, цінність людини, соціум.

The article examines the concepts, main features and characteristics of the key types of crimes against a person - murder and assaults on health. It has been proven that the division of crimes against a person into murders and assaults on health was fixed in the norms of the Lithuanian Statute. The concept of murder had both general and specific terms that reflected the way of taking life or the subjective side. It was found out that the legal note recorded the classification of murders depending on various criteria, in particular, the division depending on the form of guilt (intentional and careless). It was revealed that in the 3rd edition of the Lithuanian Statute a distinction was made between direct and indirect intent, criminal self-confidence and negligence, which affected the degree of punishment. It was established that another type of murder was established by law - depending on the state of the criminal and the victim. For the same type of murders, nobles bore less severe criminal responsibility than commoners. It has been proven that murders were divided according to gender, and for causing the death of a woman, the culprit paid a double reward. In the norms of the Lithuanian Statute, the division of intentional murders was reflected depending on the presence (qualified) or absence (simple) of aggravating circumstances. In the norms of the legal note, the division of crimes against health into several groups was

established depending on the severity of the physical damage caused to the victim (causing mutilation, wounding, beating), which also affected the degree of punishment. It was found that each species had a special terminology. The development of the legislator's views on the concept of crimes against health was reflected in the Lithuanian Statute of 1588, the norms of which recorded the diversification of types of mutilation, as well as the introduction of the principle of "talion" as punishment. It was found that crimes against health were divided according to the same criteria as murders: the form of guilt (intention or carelessness), social status and gender of the criminal and the victim, aggravating circumstances. It was established that the development of the concept of crimes against a person during the 16th century, the tendency to complicate the concept, the main features and characteristics of murder and assault on health were caused by the following reasons: the development of the spiritual sphere (increasing the level of legal awareness of the legislator, the influence of the Christian religion), the features of the social order of the Great principalities of Lithuania and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth (constancy of the status division of the population), the specifics of the internal political situation of the state (formation of vassalage relations).

Keywords: *Ukraine, Ukrainian criminal law, genesis, sources of law, types of crimes, human value, society.*

Problem statement. During the development of the legal, democratic, social state of Ukraine, the gradual formation of civil society, the historical past, the legal heritage of the Ukrainian people plays an important role. Solving the current problems associated with the reform of the legal system of the modern Ukrainian state largely depends on the scientific knowledge and assimilation of historical experience, knowledge of those law-making processes that have taken place in Ukraine over the centuries.

Among many historical and legal phenomena, the study of the development of Ukrainian criminal law in the 15th - 16th centuries is of great importance today. as a complete system that included separate structural elements (concepts, institutions, etc.). In this sense, it is important to conduct a study of the concept of crimes against a person (primarily, against life and health) in Ukrainian criminal law in the 15th - 16th centuries. After all, from an axiological point of view, human life and health are the highest social values, from an anthropological point of view, they constitute the essence of the humanistic nature of law.

It should be noted that, to a greater or lesser extent, the formed complex of knowledge about criminal encroachments on life and health as objects of crime, enshrined in normative legal acts of the 15th - 16th centuries, reflected not only the level of the legislator's awareness of the degree of their social danger, but also testified about the quality of the criminal law protection of the specified objects in the Ukrainian criminal law of the studied period.

Research of crimes against the person in the Ukrainian criminal law of the 15th - 16th centuries. will make it possible not only to find out their

characteristics and main features, but also to reveal the achievements of legal opinion of the specified period in the field of criminal law, as well as the level of legal awareness of the legislator. Considering the above, we believe that this scientific problem is relevant and requires scientific study.

Analysis of recent research and publications. It should be noted that this scientific problem is not sufficiently covered in domestic historical and legal science. There are a number of scientific works by such researchers as: Ya. Padokha, T. Koval, D. Lyubchenko, P. Muzychenka, I. Boyka, Yu. Senkiv, Yu. Kopyk, M. Korolenko, B. Tyshchuk and others. In the scientific work of these scientists, the specified problem is considered fragmentarily.

We are talking about the study of crimes against a person either in separate chronological periods (for example, at the end of the 15th century), or according to separate legal monuments (for example, according to the Code of Casimir of 1468 or the III edition of the Lithuanian Statute), or without involvement in scientific study all norms of the wide and diverse legislative material of the 15th - 16th centuries.

As an exception, we should mention the works of S. Kudin, in which the scientist addressed the solution of this problem. However, although the scientist conducted a thorough analysis of the normative framework of the 15th - 16th centuries, which contained the views of the legislator of the specified period on the essence and main features of crimes against life and health, in our opinion, the scientist's justification of the criteria for dividing crimes against life and health is insufficient.

Previously unsolved problems. Considering the above, we believe that it is necessary to investigate in more detail and comprehensively the essence and main features of crimes against a person, reflected in the entire array of the legislative base of the 15th - 16th centuries, taking into account the objective historical situation that developed on the territory of Ukraine in the specified period.

The purpose of the article. It consists in identifying the essence and main features of crimes against a person in the Ukrainian criminal law of the 15th - 16th centuries, clarifying those determinants that were characteristic of the Middle Ages and influenced their content.

Presenting main material. The development of the Ukrainian criminal law of the 15th - 16th centuries was reflected in the Lithuanian Statute. the concept of crimes against a person. One should agree with Yu.V. Senkiv, who notes that «a fairly clear system of classification of crimes was created in the Lithuanian Statute, which was based on the object of the criminal offense; in addition, crimes were also classified according to the degree of severity» [1, p. 79].

It is impossible not to take into account the fair opinion of Yu.V. Kopyk, that «crimes against a person belonged to serious crimes in the Republic of Ukraine. These are crimes based on the violation of human rights and freedoms, which are fundamental values that have determined the organization of the European community for almost half a millennium» [2, p. 161]. If we talk in general about the reasons that contributed to this process, then it is worth highlighting the influence of the value attitude in Ukrainian society to the life of a person and his health.

This was naturally reflected in the introduction by the legislator to the Lithuanian Statute of norms, which recorded various crimes against a person, in particular, against his life and health. But we can also talk about other factors that influenced the classification of crimes against a person, which led to the establishment of different degrees of punishment for their commission.

Among the crimes against the person, crimes against life took the leading place. It should be noted that the Lithuanian Statute had several terms that reflected the concept of murder (for example, «manslaughter», «murder», «stuffed his throat», «gagged», «poisoned» and others). As a rule, these terms were general (except for the specific «poisons»

and «murdered», which meant «deprived of life by poisoning or torture»).

One should agree with the opinion of S.V. Kudin, who claims «that there was a terminology that reflected the murders from the subjective side» [3, p. 154]. For example, committed intentionally – «intentionally did», «intentionally killed out of revenge», carelessly – «accidental manslaughter», «accidental murder», out of criminal self-confidence – «unintentionally» and negligently – «out of ignorance», «negligence» and other. The improvement of terminology testifies to the development of legal technology in that period.

The analysis of the Lithuanian Statute shows that it contains enough norms that refer to the dependence of murder on the form of guilt. At the same time, the punishment of murders according to the Lithuanian Statute was determined by intent or carelessness. Thus, deliberate («intentional») murder was considered to be the infliction of death in the presence of the monarch or in his palace, the monarch's envoy, in the presence of judges or the judges themselves, a court official, during a war or a bandit attack on a house or church, a commoner, a newborn child, a husband mistresses, parricide, murder of one of the spouses, parents, sister or brother, children, one's master, out of revenge, secret murder (I Edition, Chapter VII, Articles 1, 14, 15, 21; II Edition, Chapter II, Articles 23, Chapter IV, Articles 40, 41, Chapter XI, Articles 1, 3, 10, 12, 13, 16, 17, 18; Edition III, Chapter I, Articles 9, 10, 24, Chapter II, Articles 18, 21, IV Chapter, 11, 62, 63 Articles, XI Chapter, 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 16, 17, 27, 28, 29, 31, 32, 39, 60 Articles, XII Chapter, 1, 2 Articles, Chapter XIV, Article 30) [4, p. 56, 60, 62, 63; 5, p. 40, 88, 89, 149, 151, 155, 156-158, 159, 162; 6, p. 9, 10, 22, 41, 43, 101, 158, 159, 281, 284, 287-290, 295, 303, 305- 309, 314, 327, 333, 334, 379].

It is worth noting that «in practice, such crimes happened. For example, on May 28, 1563 in the village The peasants from Lyakhov of the Kremenets county carried out an armed attack on the house of their master, Matvyi Senyuta, and beat him to death, after which they fled with their families and property. The following took part in this attack: chief of the village. Voynega with his son and the inhabitants of the mentioned village (Klymko with his sons, Tysh with his sons and stepsons, Sedelnyk with hired men, Vasechko with a hired man, Dmytro with his sons, Prys with his sons and hired men, Yankovych with his sons, Chornysh with his sons), residents of

the village Kashchynets with his chieftain, chieftain of the village. Varyvodyntsi, as well as Khoma Savych from the village of Lyakhovtsi» [7, p. 46].

You can also cite another example related to a secret assassination (ambush). So, «On the night of September 4 to 5, 1564, in the village During a banquet organized by Princess Chetvertynska, Yarovitsa was seriously wounded by four bullets from an ambush of Prince Yaroslav Sangushko when he left the house at night. A few days later, the prince died. The suspect in this case was a Polish nobleman, royal noble Valenty Zelech. After several court hearings, a verdict was handed down: Valenty Zelekh did not appear in court, then he pleaded guilty to the crime, and therefore was sentenced to death for murder. Since V. Zhelech broke his oath, he was declared dishonored, an outlaw, that is, an exile whom every resident of the country had the right to kill» [8, p. 305].

Ukrainian criminal law of the studied period is characterized by the distribution of intentional murders by types of intent, which was reflected in the norms of the Lithuanian Statute. In particular, murders with direct intent can include parricide, the murder of a relative, one's master, and others, and indirect (incidental) killing of a nobleman as a result of the latter's illegal imprisonment (III Edition, Chapter XI, Article 28).

It should also be noted that the norms of the Lithuanian Statute record the division of murders committed out of carelessness («unintentional and accidental manslaughter») into murders committed both out of criminal self-confidence and negligence (III Edition, Chapter XI, Articles 11, 23).

In our opinion, at the time of the publication of the Lithuanian Statute, punishment depended on status. The most protected in this aspect was the state of the nobles; in contrast, commoners enjoyed minimal criminal and legal protection of their lives from the state. This testifies to the impact on the legal consciousness of the legislator of the features of the social system of the Lithuanian-Russian state and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, in which the nobility occupied an exclusively privileged position, which was ensured by strengthened criminal law protection of its rights.

Thus, for the «head» (that is, for the murder) of a nobleman, the criminal had to pay 100 kopecks of money; the murder of representatives of other estates was «valued» much less (from 20 to 60 kopecks of money). (I Edition, Chapter VII, Article 29,

Chapter XI, 1 Article; Edition II, Chapter XI, Articles 12, 26, Chapter XII, Articles 1, 2, 3; Edition III, Chapter XI, Articles 27, 29, 39, XII Chapter, Articles 1, 2, 3, 6) [4, p. 65, 88; 5, p. 156, 162, 166, 167; 6, p. 303, 306, 314, 333-335].

There was also a difference in the imposition of the death penalty. In particular, judges imposed the death penalty without any conditions for the murder of a nobleman by a commoner, while the death penalty was imposed for the murder of a commoner by a nobleman only when the murderer was caught «in the act». A similar gradation in the amount of property seizures sufficiently reflected the state of Ukrainian society in the 15th - 16th centuries.

A significant criterion for the division of murders into types was the gender of the criminal and the victim. Thus, the murder of a woman was punished by the payment of a double reward («the headship must be assigned twice», «And their wives are given a double headship») (I Edition, XI Chapter, 1 Article; II Edition, XI Chapter, 13 Article, XII Chapter, 1, 3 Articles; III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 27, XII Chapter, Articles 3, 5, 6) [4, p. 88; 5, p. 157, 166, 167; 6, p. 303, 334, 335], which can be explained by the special importance of a woman in the family as a mother and a housewife. Moreover, the double payment of the principality was a norm of customary law and was applied in the period that preceded the publication of the Lithuanian Statute.

It should be emphasized that the circle of women whose murder was punished by paying a double reward expanded with the publication of each new edition of the Lithuanian Statute (I Edition, XI Chapter, 1 Article; II Edition, XI Chapter, 13 Article, XII Chapter, 1, 3 Articles; III Edition, XII Chapter, 3, 6 Articles) [4, p. 88; 5, p. 157, 166, 167; 6, p. 303, 334, 335]. In our opinion, this could indicate the normative consolidation of the influence of the humanistic views of Ukrainian society on the role of women in the family and society.

Murders can also be divided depending on the presence of aggravating circumstances, which influenced the legislator's understanding of the increased public danger of this category of murders. All murders with aggravating circumstances (qualified) were intentional, they were distinguished from other types of murder by several features: the nature of the relationship between the killer and the victim (family or familial), the relationship between the master and the servant (vassal), combination with other crimes (for example, with a bandit attack,

robbery, etc.), the method of committing (insidiousness), if the person killed was a public servant, the motive (revenge), special immorality (I Edition, VII Chapter, 1, 14 Articles; II Edition, XI Chapter, 1, 10, 16, 18 Articles; III Edition, I Chapter, 24 Article; II Chapter, 18 Article, IV Chapter, 7, 11, 40 Articles, XI Chapter, 1, 7, 10, 16, 17, 18 Articles, XIV Chapter, 30 Article). These crimes were punished more severely than other murders (it is mostly a qualified death penalty, with deprivation of honor (for nobles) and mandatory payment of a head tax).

To simple murders (that is, without aggravating circumstances), the legislator included infanticide (II Edition, XI Chapter, Article 16; III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 7), causing the death of a nobleman by his illegal imprisonment (III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 28), causing death to a person by a lunatic (III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 35), as well as murder: in a fight (duel) (III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 14), of a person whose identity cannot be determined (II Edition, XI Chapter, Article 31; III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 26), *benkarta* (*baystruka*, *bezbatchenka*) (III Edition, XIV Chapter, Article 32), during a fight or during a fight, but when the person was in a state of necessary defense (I Edition, VII Chapter, Articles 23, 24; II Edition, XI Chapter, 26, 27 Articles; III Edition, XI Chapter, Articles 10, 11, 22), a servant of a person who attacked his master (I Edition, VII Chapter, Article 26; II Edition, XI Chapter, Articles 29; III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 25), manslaughter (III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 23) and others.

As you can see, the main features of simple murders are the absence of malice, treachery, revenge, and in many cases, intentionality. For such types of murder, «for which the most severe form of punishment was a simple death penalty - beheading, imprisonment could also be imposed, as well as the payment of a fine» [9, p. 77].

It should be noted that other types of classification of murders have developed in Ukrainian historiography. Some scientists present the following division of murders: qualified, privileged, separate types; J. Padoh divides murders into heavy, ordinary and light; S.V. Kudin and D.I. Lyubchenko - for simple and with aggravating circumstances [10, p. 40; 3, p. 155-156; 9, p. 77].

The development of the concept of crimes against personal health was reflected in the norms of the Lithuanian Statute. The Lithuanian Statute is characterized by the presence of a significant number

of terms reflecting the concept of «dismemberment» (this concept is used by a number of Ukrainian authors, but we tend to use another concept («causing mutilation to a person»), which, in our opinion, is more approximate from a philological point of view reflects this type of crime against health).

Mutilation, depending on the damage caused, was denoted by such terms as «cut off», «cut off» (hand, leg, nose, ear, finger, lip), «knocked out» (teeth), «blinded» (eye) and others (I Edition, Chapter VII, Article 9; Edition II, Chapter XI, Article 13; Edition III, Chapter XI, Article 27) [4, p. 59; 5, p. 157; 6, p. 302]. It should be noted that the legislator divided mutilation according to the severity of the damage: for removing a finger - 20 kopecks, for a head injury - 100 kopecks, other injuries were punished with compensation of 50 kopecks.

It is interesting that with the publication of each subsequent revision of the Lithuanian Statute, the list of organs whose damage is punishable increases (yes, damage to the ears and lips is added). Loss of speech due to severe head injury was equated to causing mutilation.

It should be noted that in the Lithuanian Statute of 1588, unlike previous editions, causing mutilation was already punished according to the principle of «talion» («the same punishment and the same members»). Although, at the same time, the Lithuanian Statute of 1529 provided for a fine, and the Lithuanian Statute of 1566 provided for imprisonment.

The period under study also saw the development of the concept of wounding («injured», «wounded»), which, although they had serious consequences, were not associated with causing mutilation. Based on the analysis of the norms of the Lithuanian Statute, injuries can be classified depending on their severity.

Thus, the most serious injury was a wound on the face and a wound on the head, followed by damage to other body organs under the condition of temporary loss (up to 1 year) of their functions (a bloody wound on the head and other injuries, moreover, caused by iron objects) («but b from that injury he was so severely lame that he could not use his leg for a year») (1 Edition, Chapter VII, Article 9; II Edition, XI Chapter, Article 13; III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 27) [4, p. 59; 5, p. 157; 6, p. 302-303].

Such a division naturally affected the amount of compensation for damage («injury»): for damage to body organs, due to which there was a

temporary loss of their functions (up to 1 year) - 50 kopecks, if the person was damaged in more than one organ (50 kopecks), and two, or she lost the ability to speak because of a wound to the head (100 kopecks), for causing a wound on the face, the culprit paid 40 kopecks, for a wound on the head - 30 kopecks, for an injury with iron objects - 20 kopecks, etc.

It should be noted that practice shows that injuries were the most common types of crimes against health. Yes, the archival material contains many complaints specifically about causing injuries to a person. As an example, we will cite fairly typical complaints: «complaint of Volodymyr Hrodsky judge Ivan Kalusovsky against Mr. Bartos Vytvynsky for causing injuries to the complainant, Ivan's brother, and a servant while they were visiting the latter»; «complaint of the servant of Prince Janusz Porytskyi - Martyn Lyakhovskyi about the infliction of injuries on him by some Stetsk, who served under Prince Pyotr Porytskyi in the village of Hrykovychy» [11, sheet 30; 12, sheet 47].

As for beatings (the corresponding terms were «beat», «hit», «pushed», «pushed»), in the studied period they were qualified as pushing a person or beating him with hands. As can be seen from the study of the articles of the Lithuanian Statute, the legal note distinguishes between them, taking into account the gravity of the consequences of each of these crimes. Thus, the infliction of beatings was punished less severely than the infliction of wounds (I Edition, VI Chapter, Article 21; II Edition, IV Chapter, Article 39, XI Chapter, 13 Article; III Edition, IV Chapter, Article 62, XI Chapter, 27 Article).

Causing mutilation, wounding and beating can be classified according to the same criteria as murder. For example, depending on the form of guilt, unintentionally causing mutilation or injury was punished less severely than intentional (I Edition, Chapter VII, Articles 1, 23, 24, 25; II Edition, Chapter XI, Articles 1, 18, 26, 27, 28; III Edition, XI Chapter, Articles 16, 17, 24, 27).

The division of crimes against health according to the social status of the victim and the criminal also had an impact on the degree of punishment. The Lithuanian Statute provided for different degrees of punishment for committing crimes against the health of a nobleman and a commoner. The punishment was also different depending on the gender of the victim. In particular, women received a double reward for causing them mutilation and causing

beatings (I Edition, XI Chapter, Articles 1, 5; II Edition, XI Chapter, Articles 13, 15, XII Chapter, 1, 2, 3 Articles; III Edition, XI Chapter, Articles 16, 27, 39, Chapter XII, Articles 3, 4, 5, 6).

As with murder, among the assaults on health, it is possible to track those that in the studied period belonged to crimes with aggravating circumstances. The legislator considered them to be a combination of crimes against health with other crimes (I Edition, Chapter VI, Articles 21, 22, Chapter VII, Article 1; Edition II, Chapter IV, Articles 39, 40, 41, Chapter XI, Article 1; III Edition, I Chapter, 9, 10 Articles, II Chapter, 18 Article, IV Chapter, 62, 63 Articles, XI Chapter, 1 Article), vassal relations between master and servant (III Edition, XI Chapter, 9 Article), motive (III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 16) and the method of committing the crime (III Edition, XI Chapter, Article 17) [4, p. 56, 63; 5, p. 150, 157-159, 162, 166, 167; 6, p. 295, 300, 302, 303, 314, 334, 335].

Conclusions. Thus, on the basis of the above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. In the norms of the Lithuanian Statute, the legislator recorded a clear division of crimes against a person into murders and assaults on health. The concept of murder had both general and specific terms that reflected the way of taking life or the subjective side. The Lithuanian Statute established the classification of murders depending on various criteria. First, it is a division depending on the form of guilt (intentional and careless); at the same time, in the III edition of the Lithuanian Statute, the legislator singles out direct and indirect intent, criminal self-confidence and negligence. This division also affected the degree of punishment.

Normatively, another type of murder was established - depending on the state of the criminal and the victim. For the same type of murders, nobles bore less severe criminal responsibility than commoners. Murders were also divided according to gender: for causing the death of a woman, the culprit paid a double reward. In the norms of the Lithuanian Statute, the division of intentional murders was reflected depending on the presence (qualified) or absence (simple) of aggravating circumstances. Qualified murders were punished more severely.

2. In the norms of the Lithuanian Statute, the division of crimes against health into several groups was established depending on the severity of the physical damage caused to the victim (causing mutilation, injury, beating), which also affected the

degree of punishment. Moreover, each species had a special terminology. There was also an internal division of mutilation and injuries depending on the severity of the damage, which affected the increase in the amount of compensation. The development of the legislator's views on the concept of crimes against health was reflected in the Lithuanian Statute of 1588, the norms of which recorded the diversification of types of mutilation, as well as the introduction of the principle of "talion" as punishment.

Crimes against health were divided according to the same criteria as murders. They were: form of guilt (intention or carelessness), social status and gender of the criminal and the victim, aggravating circumstances. All the specified criteria were taken

into account by the legislator when assigning a more or less severe punishment to the guilty party.

3. The gradual development of the concept of crimes against the person during the 16th century, the tendency to complicate the concept, the main features and characteristics of murder and assault on health were caused by several factors: the development of the spiritual sphere (increasing the level of legal awareness of the legislator, the influence of the Christian religion), features of the social order of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth (constancy of the population by age), the specifics of the state's internal political situation (formation of vassalage relations).

References:

1. Senkiv Yu. V. Poniattia ta vydy zlochyniv u pravi Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho. *Chasopys Kyivskoho universytetu prava*. 2008. № 4. S. 77-82.
2. Kopyk Yu. V. Kryminalne pravo na ukrainskykh zemliakh u skladi Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho: dys. ... kand. yuryd. nauk: 12.00.01. Lviv: Lviv. nats. un-t imeni Ivana Franka, 2015. 220 s.
3. Kudin S. V. Stanovlennia i rozvytok kryminalnoho prava Ukrainy u X – pershii polovyni XVII st.: dys. kand. yuryd. nauk: 12.00.01. Kyiv: Kyiv. nats. un-t imeni Tarasa Shevchenka, 2001. 226 s.
4. Statuty Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho: u 3 t. / za red. S. Kivalova, P. Muzychenka, A. Pankova. Odesa: Yurydychna literatura, 2002. T. 1: Statut Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho 1529 roku. 2002. 464 s.
5. Statuty Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho: u 3 t. / za red. S. Kivalova, P. Muzychenka, A. Pankova. Odesa: Yurydychna literatura, 2003. T. 2: Statut Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho 1566 roku. 2003. 560 s.
6. Statuty Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho: u 3 t. / za red. S. Kivalova, P. Muzychenka, A. Pankova. Odesa: Yurydychna literatura, 2004. T. 3 (kn. 1): Statut Velykoho kniazivstva Lytovskoho 1588 roku. 2004. 672 s.
7. Arkhiv Pivdenno-Zakhidnoi Rusi [Arkheohrafichna komisiia]. T. 1. Ch. 6. Akty pro ekonomichni ta yurydychni vidnosyny selian v XVI – XVIII st. K., 1876. 614 s.
8. XX Arkhiv Sanhushkov v Slavuti. [red. Radziminskiy]. Krakiv: Z drukarni Natsionalnoho zakladu imeni rodyny Oslinskykh pid kerivnytstvom Karolia Yasinskoho, 1910. T. 6. 389 s.
9. Liubchenko D. I. Rozvytok kryminalnoho prava Hetmanshchyny u druhii polovyni XVII – XVIII st.: dys. ... kand. yuryd. nauk: 12.00.01. Kyiv: Akad. pratsi i sots. v-n, 2005. 204 s.
10. Padokh Ya. Narys istorii ukrainskoho karnoho prava. Miunkhen: Molode zhyttia, 1951. 128 s.
11. F. 28 Volodymyrskyi hrodskyi sud. op. 1 Spr. 1. Aktova knyha 2 kvitnia – 30 serpnia 1566 r., 130 ark.
12. F. 28 Volodymyrskyi hrodskyi sud. op. 1 Spr. 2. Aktova knyha 23 sichnia – 31 hrudnia 1567 r., 222 ark.